

Cone Beam Computed Tomography in Pediatric Dentistry: A Review

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Abstract

Introduction: The aim of this study was to find the reasons for referral, estimate the effective, cumulative, and organ absorbed doses and risks. **Methods and Materials:** The articles published in English language from 2000 to 2020 in PUBMED/MEDLINE and google scholar were searched electronically. Using Cone Beam Computed Tomography, dental radiography, pediatric dentistry, as search terms. Twenty-two papers were selected after applying all inclusion and exclusion criteria, and critically reviewed for the comparison of outcomes. **Results:** patients were referred to undergo CBCT scans in the following order of priority; developing dentition-generalized/localized, dento-alveolar reasons, periodontics, surgical applications, endodontic, and the visualization of the TMJ. Children exposed to CBCT had a higher median effective dose and cumulative dose than conventional radiographs. **Conclusion:** CBCT is recommended when the benefits oversight the potential risk of exposure. **Keywords:** Cone Beam Computed Tomography, dental radiography, pediatric dentistry

Introduction

The use of CBCT in children population has recently increased. Cone Beamed Computed Tomography with 3-D technology is a replacement for conventional 2-D imaging and has a wide application among child patients in pediatric dentistry. CBCT was developed in the late 90s by Arai et al. in Japan and independently at the same time by Mozzo et al. in Italy. The device contains a rotating gantry with both x-ray source and detector attached to it (the C-arm). It has advantages such as high resolution images, less disturbed images from metal artifacts, potential for vertical scanning imaging, user-friendly viewing software. Patients are referred to take CBCT for a variety of reasons. Generally, the cases could be divided into seven groups as follows: (1) dental anomalies including monitoring tooth eruption, treatment planning, and follow-up in orthodontics (2) impacted teeth, (3) orofacial cleft, (4) orthognathic surgery including preoperative or postoperative CBCT examinations, (5) endodontics, (6) bone pathosis including cystic or tumoral bone lesions, inflammatory bone lesions, bone changes in systemic diseases, maxillary sinus diseases, and TMJ disorders. and (7) dentoalveolar trauma including all traumatic dental lesions with or without alveolar process involvement and more complex maxillofacial trauma including TMJ fractures. The aim of this study was to estimate the referral reasons, their correlation with age, gender, field of view, and resolution, the effective, cumulative, and organ doses in children exposed to CBCT for various conditions.

Methods and Materials

The articles published in English language from 2000 to 2020 in PUBMED/MEDLINE and google scholar were searched electronically. Using Cone Beam Computed Tomography, dental radiography, pediatric dentistry, as search terms. Twenty-two papers were selected after applying all inclusion and exclusion criteria, and critically reviewed for the comparison of outcomes.

Results

Clinical conditions	number	Age (years) mean	Multiple CBCT a (%)	CBCT protocol (FOV) (%)			Effective Dose (μ Sv)				Cumulative dose (μ Sv)		
				S	M	L	Median	Q3	Min	Max	Median	Q3	IQR
Dental anomalies	436	13.4	37.0	17.4	11.9	70.6	151.5	176.2	22	353	471.5	730.0	509.7
Impacted teeth	230	12.8	13.4	62.1	29.1	20.8	125.3	141.2	18	218	193.1	246.7	78.7
Orofacial cleft	24	13.1	11.5	8.3	16.6	75.0	146	184.7	60	307	251.2	353.0	168.0
Orthognathic surgery	28	16.5	40.0	-	-	100.0	102.6	145.5	71	212	443.5	623.7	278.2
endodontics	62	12.6	15.5	88.7	9.6	1.6	127.8	131.4	26	183	207.4	255.5	91.5
Bone pathosis	54	13.0	6.7	35.1	29.6	35.1	129.5	151.7	30	252	231.6	310.8	132.7
Dentoalveolar trauma	41	11.0	8.2	34.1	36.5	53.6	123.4	149.5	27	262	191.1	259.0	90.0
overall	875	12.9	25.1	35	17	47	137.9	158.6	17.4	352.5	231.4	403.6	224.3

Discussion

According to aforementioned result, a higher radiation dose of children with dental anomalies could be explained by the use of large FOV, the number of CBCT examinations and multiple exposures. The children who underwent a CBCT examination only after the age of 16 years, resulting in a relatively lower dose. In the above mention study, the influence of scanning protocol on organ doses was also demonstrated. When patients were irradiated with large FOV, the salivary gland, brain, and RBM were included inside the primary beam, while for small and medium FOV, the brain is only exposed to scatter radiation. Thus, the results of the present study revealed the differences in organ exposures on CBCT according to FOV. Furthermore, the highest organ dose was found for the salivary glands in all CBCT scan protocols, without significant differences between FOVs. An explanation could be the fact that the parotid gland, which is the largest salivary gland, and the upper part of the mouth are always located in the primary beam of CBCT. Mihaela et al reported that Fourteen percent of referrals were for dento-alveolar trauma, 18% for other dento-alveolar reasons, 4 % for developing dentition-generalized, 36 % for developing dentition-localized, 10 % for endodontics, 1 % for periodontics, 16 % for surgical applications, and 1 % was for the visualization of the TMJ. The same study displayed that there seemed to be a correlation between orthodontic referrals and female patients. The majority of patients referred for trauma follow-up were 12 years and older. Jakob et al reported that Fisher's exact tests showed that by gender, FOV ($p=0.374$) as well as the resolution ($p=1$), did not differ. There was no correlation between age group and FOV ($p=0.492$, Fisher's exact test) and between age group and resolution ($p=0.038$, Fisher's exact test). the other study reported that the Life Attributable Risk (LAR) and Relative Radiation Level (RRL) were significantly higher for children exposed to CBCT under the age of 18. The CBCT doses and radiation risk vary but remain in the lower levels of the relative risk of medical exposures. The American Academy of Oral and Maxillofacial Radiology (AAOMR) has revealed the efficacy of CBCT for dental anomalies and treatment planning in moderate and severe skeletal discrepancies and the median age of children exposed to CBCT was found to be 12 years. It is noteworthy that there is a lack of epidemiological evidence for a direct relationship between the dental medical exposure to low dose radiation and an increased risk of cancer. however, Children could have a potentially higher risk for radiation-induced cancer occurrence due to their longer life span and their higher radiosensitivity compared with adults.

Conclusion

CBCT is recommended when the benefits oversight the potential risk of exposure, moreover the use of low-dose protocols by adjusting the field of view (FOV) and exposure parameters according to the dental clinical condition along with a well-informed justification of the CBCT examination allows the decrease in the radiation dose in children.

References

1. Marcu M, et al. Estimation of the radiation dose for pediatric CBCT indications: a prospective study on ProMax3D. *Int J Paediatr Dent.* 2018;28(3):300-309.
2. Mihaela h, et al. Irradiation provided by dental radiological procedures in a pediatric Population. *Eur. J. Radiol.* 2018;103:103-112
3. Jakob W. G. Van Acker, Luc C. Martens, Johan K. M. Aps. Cone-beam computed tomography in pediatric dentistry, a retrospective observational study. *Clin Oral Invest.* 2016;20(5):1003-10